

Microwave assisted one pot 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions of novel dihydropyran derived nitron

Bhaskar Chakraborty* and Prawin Kumar Sharma

Organic Chemistry Laboratory, Sikkim Government College, Gangtok-737 102, Sikkim, India

E-mail : bchakraborty42@gmail.com

Manuscript received 20 April 2011, revised 19 September 2011, accepted 17 October 2011

Abstract : Microwave assisted 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions of novel dihydropyran derived nitron with various dipolarophiles have been studied *in situ* and found to afford novel isoxazolidine derivatives with high selectivity and synthetic potentials.

Keywords : MWI, cycloaddition reaction, novel isoxazolidines, amino alcohols.

Introduction

The synthetic utility of microwave irradiation in organic synthesis has increased considerably in recent years¹⁻⁵. This nonconventional energy source is able to reduce chemical reaction times and to increase yields, and in some cases can lead to outcomes different from those obtained with conventional heating. Microwave reactions are quite often cleaner, faster, and higher-yielding than conventional ones. This methodology can be regarded as environmentally friendly, mainly because solvent-free reactions are especially suited to microwave conditions^{6,7}. Microwave technology has been successfully used to perform difficult cycloadditions and to obtain temperature sensitive compounds. Particularly interesting is 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition, which represents one of the most versatile tools for the construction of five-membered heterocycles. Owing to the labile nature of the N-O bond under mild reducing conditions, isoxazolidines provide easy access to a variety of fascinating 1,3-difunctional amino alcohols⁸. In fact, 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition was one of the first microwave assisted organic reactions to be explored. In continuation of our green methodological synthesis of spiro isoxazolidine, isoxazolidine, isoxazoline, aldehyde, ketone synthesis using α -chloro and α -amino nitrones in solid phase and in hydrated media⁹⁻¹⁷, we report herein microwave assisted 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reactions of novel dihydropyran derived nitron leading to the green synthesis of novel isoxazolidine derivatives with high selectivity and excellent yield (Scheme 1;

Table 1). Synthetic potential of the novel isoxazolidine derivatives (2-4) are tremendous as they could be converted into acyclic chiral 1,3 difunctional amino alcohols (Scheme 2; Table 2) by the reductive cleavage of the N-O bond when treated with zinc powder in dilute acetic acid under microwave irradiation¹⁸⁻²⁰.

Results and discussion

In the present study the formation of nitron **1** has been achieved by treating 2,3-dihydro-4*H*-pyran with *N*-phenylhydroxylamine under microwave irradiation and has been trapped *in situ* by different maleimides in 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reaction with high selectivity resulting isoxazolidines (2-4) (Scheme 1; Table 1). Dimerization of nitron could also be controlled under this condition. Induction of three asymmetric centres at C₅, C₄ and C₃ positions of the newly developed isoxazolidine derivatives have made this one pot synthesis highly attractive. The development of diastereomers can be rationalized by an *exo* approach of nitron **1** which has *Z* configuration for the formation of major cycloadducts **2a-4a** (transition state 1). The minor cycloadducts **2b-4b** are formed by the *endo* approach of *Z* nitron (transition state 2). The mixture of diastereomers are identified by considering the multiplicity of the proton signals at 3-H and 4-H along with their coupling constant values^{21,22}. The most significant differences in the ¹H NMR data for the diastereomers are the position and multiplicity of the 3-H signal. In the major adducts **2a-4a**, coupling constant

Table 1. Physicochemical data of synthesized compounds (**2a-4a**; **2b-4b**)

Entry	Nitron	Dipolarophile ^a	Time (min)	Cycloadduct and m.p (°C)		<i>cis/trans</i> ratio	Yield (%)
				2a-4a : <i>cis</i> ; 2b-4b : <i>trans</i>			
1	<i>N</i> -Phenyl-5-hydroxynitron	<i>N</i> -Methyl maleimide	7 (13 h)	2a : White crystals, 95	2a : 64	96 (54)	
				2b : White crystals, 82	2b : 32		
2	<i>N</i> -Phenyl-5-hydroxynitron	<i>N</i> -Phenyl maleimide	9 (14 h)	3a : Pale yellow solid, 108	3a : 68	93 (52)	
				3b : White solid, 103	3b : 25		
3	<i>N</i> -Phenyl-5-hydroxynitron	<i>N</i> -Cyclohexyl maleimide	9 (14 h)	4a : Yellow crystals, 80	4a : 62	93 (47)	
				4b : Yellow crystals, 88	4b : 31		

^aReaction condition : DHP (1 mmol), *N*-phenylhydroxylamine (1 equivalent), dipolarophile (1 equivalent), MWI (250 W).

^bIsolated yields after purification.

Figures in parentheses indicate reactions performed in conventional method.

between 3-H and 4-H has been measured as $J_{3,4} \sim 6.26$ Hz whilst for minor adducts **2b-4b**, $J_{3,4}$ is ~ 2.54 Hz. These differences can be explained by considering the available isoxazolidine ring conformations. Due to the

4,5-fused pyrrolidindione, the isoxazolidine ring adopts an envelope conformation and allowing for inversion, its nitrogen atom will either extend out from the envelope, i.e. minor conformation, or point inside the envelope,

Note

i.e. major conformation. The minor conformer has the *N*-lone pair antiperiplanar and therefore, capable of shielding 3-H proton, so this conformation is assigned to the minor conformer (Fig. 1). The diastereomeric isoxazolidines **2a-4a** and **2b-4b** were separated by column chromatography and obtained in analytically pure form by recrystallization from heptane-ethyl acetate²³.

1,3-amino alcohols using other isoxazolidine derivatives (**2b-4b**) are in progress at present.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded with a Bruker Avance DRX-300 spectrometer (300 MHz, FT

Fig. 1

In all the diastereomers, the configurations of H-5 and H-4 are *cis* as evidenced from their coupling constant values. In general, the reactions are very clean and high yielding compared to usual cycloaddition reactions of nitrones. The products have been characterized from their spectroscopic (IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, MS) data. No catalyst or co-organic solvent is required.

The newly developed novel *N*-phenyl isoxazolidine derivatives (**2a-4a**) can be easily converted into acyclic chiral 1,3 difunctional amino alcohols (**2c-4c**) (Scheme 2; Table 2) by the reductive cleavage of the N-O bond. These conversions have been achieved by simply treating the substrates with zinc powder in dilute acetic acid under microwave irradiation¹⁸⁻²⁰.

The relative configurations of H-1, H-2 and H-3 protons of the newly developed 1,3-amino alcohols (**2c-4c**) are *syn* as evidenced from their coupling constant values ($J_{\text{H}1,\text{H}2} \sim 6.70$ Hz; $J_{\text{H}2,\text{H}3} \sim 6.10$ Hz). Expected broad signals for N-H proton around δ 3.40 and alcoholic OH groups around δ 5.20 ppm are also obtained. Synthesis of

NMR) using TMS as internal standard. ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on the same instrument at 75 MHz. The coupling constants (*J*) are given in Hz. IR spectra were obtained with a Perkin-Elmer RX 1-881 machine as film or as KBr pellets for all the products. MS spectra were recorded with a Jeol SX-102 (FAB) instrument. Elemental analyses (CHN) were performed with a Perkin-Elmer 2400 series CHN Analyzer. TLC's were run on Fluka silica gel precoated TLC plates. All other reagents and solvents were purified after receiving from commercial suppliers. *N*-Phenylhydroxylamine was prepared following standard methods available in literature. Microwave assisted reactions were carried out using domestic microwave oven KENSTER (19LKH, 19SSLM, 800 W, 2450 MHz).

General procedure for cycloaddition reaction (conventional) :

N-Phenylhydroxylamine (250 mg, 2.29 mmol) was added to a solution of 2,3-dihydro-4*H*-pyran (192 mg, 1

- (i) MWI, 9-10 min
 2 : R₂, R₃ = -CONMeCO-
 3 : R₂, R₃ = -CONPhCO-
 4 : R₂, R₃ = -CONCyCO-
 R₁ = -(CH₂)₄-OH

Scheme 2

Table 2. Physicochemical data of synthesized 1,3-amino alcohols (2c-4c)

Entry	Isoxazolidine	Reagent ^a	Time (min)	1,3-Amino alcohol (2c-4c)	Yield ^b
1	2a	Zn and dilute acetic acid	9	2c : Yellowish white gummy liquid	84
2	3a	Zn and dilute acetic acid	10	3c : White gummy liquid	81
3	4a	Zn and dilute acetic acid	10	4c : Dark gray gummy liquid	80

^aReaction condition : Isoxazolidine (250 mg), Zn (5 mg), glacial acetic acid (3 mL), MWI (250 W).

^bIsolated yields after purification.

equivalent) in dry benzene (20 mL) under N₂ atmosphere and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 24 h while the progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC (hexane : ethyl acetate = 5 : 1; R_f = 0.38). Dipolarophiles were added (1 equivalent) at this stage and the reaction mixture was further refluxed for 13-14 h. The solvent was evaporated off and the cycloadducts (2-4; Table 1) were isolated by column chromatography using benzene-pet. ether as eluent. But this methodology was discarded because of lengthy reaction process, poor yield and use of benzene as solvent.

General procedure for cycloaddition for diastereomers (MWI) :

A mixture of *N*-phenylhydroxylamine (250 mg, 2.29 mmol), 2,3-dihydro-4*H*-pyran (192 mg, 1 equivalent) was taken in a 25 mL Erlenmeyer flask, mixed well and subjected to microwave irradiation at 250 W for 5 min. The formation of nitron was monitored by TLC (hexane : ethyl acetate = 5 : 1; R_f = 0.38). *N*-Methyl maleimide (254 mg, 1 equivalent) was added at this stage and the

reaction mixture was further irradiated at 250 W for 7 min. The completion of the reaction was monitored by TLC (hexane : ethyl acetate = 5 : 1; R_f = 0.44, 0.50). The reaction mixture was cooled to RT and extracted with diethyl ether. The products were concentrated in a rotary evaporator and finally the mixture of diastereomers were purified and separated by column chromatography using ethyl acetate-hexane to afford pure isoxazolidine derivatives 2a and 2b (entry 1). This procedure was followed for other substrates listed in Table 1.

(3R,3aS,6aR)-Dihydro-3-(4-hydroxybutyl)-5-methyl-2-phenyl-2*H*-pyrrolo[3,4-*d*]isoxazole-4,6(5*H*,6*a*-*H*)-dione (2a) :

White crystals. Yield 64%; R_f = 0.44 (hexane : ethyl acetate = 5 : 1); IR (KBr) : ν_{max} 3640-3530 (br), 2915 (m), 2832 (m), 1774 (s), 1680 (s), 1440 (m), 1380 (m), 772 (s) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) : δ 6.88-6.73 (5H, m, C₆H₅), 4.83 (1H, br, s, OH, exchanged in D₂O), 4.64 (1H, d, *J* 6.3 Hz, C₃H), 4.23 (1H, dd, *J* 6.0, 6.0 Hz, C₄H), 3.30 (3H, s, CH₃ protons), 2.78 (1H, dt, *J* 6.4, 6.5 Hz, C₃H), 2.36 (2H, dt~m, CH₂ protons of

$-CH_2-(CH_2)_3OH$), 1.80–1.53 (6H, m, CH_3 protons); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) : δ 176.22, 176.10 (carbonyl carbons), 130.62, 130.16, 128.88, 128.15 (aromatic carbons), 87.15 (C_3), 76.42 (C_5), 66.23 (CH_2OH), 55.50 (C_4), 38.00 (CH_3), 25.76, 22.31, 20.27 ($3CH_2$ carbons); FAB-MS : m/z 304 (M^+), 289, 231, 227, 212, 154 (B.P), 77, 73 (Found : C, 63.02; H, 6.35; N, 9.17. $C_{16}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires : C, 63.13; H, 6.61; N, 9.21%).

(3S,3aS,6aR)-Dihydro-3-(4-hydroxybutyl)-5-methyl-2-phenyl-2H-pyrrolo[3,4-d]isoxazole-4,6(5H,6a-H)-dione (2b) :

White crystals. Yield 32%; R_f = 0.50 (hexane : ethyl acetate = 5 : 1); IR (KBr) : ν_{max} 3645–3550 (br), 2910 (m), 2830 (m), 1776 (s), 1676 (s), 1440 (m), 1385 (m), 775 (s) cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 300 MHz) : δ 6.76–6.63 (5H, m, C_6H_5), 5.04 (1H, br, s, OH, exchanged in D_2O), 4.80 (1H, d, J 3.7 Hz, C_5H), 4.15 (1H, dd, J 2.1, 2.6 Hz, C_4H), 3.34 (3H, s, CH_3 protons), 2.70 (1H, dt, J 3.1, 2.8 Hz, C_3H), 2.08 (2H, dt~m, CH_2 protons of $-CH_2(CH_2)_3OH$), 1.76–1.40 (6H, m, CH_2 protons); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) : δ 170.90, 170.17 (carbonyl carbons), 129.12, 128.75, 128.53, 127.33 (aromatic carbons), 85.56 (C_5), 73.21 (C_3), 63.08 (CH_2OH), 54.22 (C_4), 34.44 (CH_3), 23.63, 22.70, 22.12 ($3CH_2$ carbons); FAB-MS : m/z 304 (M^+), 289, 231, 230, 227, 212, 154 (B.P), 77, 73 (Found : C, 62.98; H, 6.40; N, 9.09. $C_{16}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires : C, 63.13; H, 6.61; N, 9.21%).

(3R,3aS,6aR)-Dihydro-3-(4-hydroxybutyl)-2,5-diphenyl-2H-pyrrolo[3,4-d]isoxazole-4,6(5H,6a-H)-dione (3a) :

Pale yellow solid. Yield 68%; R_f = 0.56 (hexane : ethyl acetate = 5 : 1); IR (KBr) : ν_{max} 3585–3453 (br), 2920 (m), 2835 (m), 1780 (s), 1684 (s), 1600 (s), 1480 (m), 1346 (m), 770 (s) cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 300 MHz) : δ 7.49–7.26 (2 \times 5H, m, C_6H_5), 6.84 (1H, br, s, OH, exchanged in D_2O), 4.95 (1H, d, J 6.5 Hz, C_5H), 3.91 (1H, dt, J 6.0, 6.1 Hz, C_3H), 3.55 (1H, dd, J 6.1, 6.2 Hz, C_4H), 1.90 (2H, dt~m, CH_2 protons of $-CH_2-(CH_2)_3OH$), 1.63 (6H, m, $3CH_2$ protons); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) : δ 172.12, 171.86 (carbonyl carbons), 133.77, 133.14, 132.22, 131.78, 129.80, 129.61, 128.15, 127.72 (aromatic carbons), 87.80 (C_5), 75.18 (C_3), 65.27 (CH_2OH), 56.37 (C_4), 34.55, 26.40, 25.00 ($3CH_2$ carbons); FAB-MS : m/z 366 (M^+), 306, 293, 289, 216 (B.P), 77, 73, 59 (Found : C, 68.67; H, 5.83; N, 7.52. $C_{21}H_{22}O_4N_2$ requires : C, 68.82; H, 6.04; N, 7.65%).

(3S,3aS,6aR)-Dihydro-3-(4-hydroxybutyl)-2,5-diphenyl-2H-pyrrolo[3,4-d]isoxazole-4,6(5H,6a-H)-dione (3b) :

White solid. Yield 25%; R_f = 0.48 (hexane : ethyl acetate = 5 : 1); IR (KBr) : ν_{max} 3590–3476 (br), 2934 (m), 2830 (m), 1780 (s), 1680 (s), 1610 (s), 1476 (m), 1340 (m), 776 (s) cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 300 MHz) : δ 7.36–7.15 (2 \times 5H, m, C_6H_5), 6.25 (1H, br, s, OH, exchanged in D_2O), 4.48 (1H, d, J 2.7 Hz, C_5H), 3.54 (1H, dt, J 3.0, 2.8 Hz, C_3H), 3.12 (1H, dd, J 2.2, 2.1 Hz, C_4H), 1.84 (2H, dt~m, CH_2 protons of $-CH_2-(CH_2)_3OH$), 1.50 (6H, m, $3CH_2$ protons); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) : δ 170.63, 170.14 (carbonyl carbons), 131.62, 131.08, 130.27, 130.14, 129.19, 128.40, 128.05, 127.58 (aromatic carbons), 88.06 (C_5), 73.90 (C_3), 62.83 (CH_2OH), 53.45 (C_4), 31.72, 24.44, 23.19 ($3CH_2$ carbons); FAB-MS : m/z 366 (M^+), 306, 293, 289, 216 (B.P), 212, 77, 73, 59 (Found : C, 68.63; H, 5.87; N, 7.60. $C_{21}H_{22}O_4N_2$ requires : C, 68.82; H, 6.04; N, 7.65%).

(3R,3aS,6aR)-5-Cyclohexyl-dihydro-3-(4-hydroxybutyl)-2-phenyl-2H-pyrrolo[3,4-d]isoxazole-4,6(5H,6a-H)-dione (4a) :

Yellow crystals. Yield 62%, R_f = 0.50 (hexane : ethyl acetate = 5 : 1); IR (KBr) : ν_{max} 3638–3515 (br), 2865 (s), 1785 (s), 1680 (s), 1446 (m), 1380 (m), 1265 (m), 780 (s) cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$, 300 MHz) : δ 7.40–7.17 (5H, m, C_6H_5), 5.94 (1H, d, J 6.6 Hz, C_5H), 4.40 (1H, br, s, OH, exchanged in D_2O), 3.44 (1H, dd, J 6.2, 6.0 Hz, C_4H), 2.23 (1H, dt, J 6.6, 6.1 Hz, C_3H), 1.69 (2H, dt~m, CH_2 protons of $-CH_2-(CH_2)_3OH$), 1.45 (17H, m, cyclohexyl and CH_2 protons); ^{13}C NMR ($CDCl_3$) : δ 173.16, 171.37 (carbonyl carbons), 136.04, 135.52, 134.07, 133.93 (aromatic carbons), 86.80 (C_5), 77.08 (C_3), 62.50 (CH_2OH), 55.62 (C_4), 38.51, 36.07, 34.40, 31.10, 29.52, 27.70, 26.30, 25.00, 23.28 (cyclohexyl and CH_2 carbons); FAB-MS : m/z 372 (M^+), 313, 299, 222 (B.P), 216, 83, 77, 73, 59 (Found : C, 67.62; H, 7.43; N, 7.35. $C_{21}H_{28}O_4N_2$ requires : C, 67.71; H, 7.56; N, 7.52%).

(3S,3aS,6aR)-5-Cyclohexyl-dihydro-3-(4-hydroxybutyl)-2-phenyl-2H-pyrrolo[3,4-d]isoxazole-4,6(5H,6a-H)-dione (4b) :

Yellow crystals. Yield 31%, R_f = 0.44 (hexane : ethyl acetate = 5 : 1); IR (KBr) : ν_{max} 3623–3534 (br), 2880 (s), 1782 (s), 1680 (s), 1440 (m), 1385 (m), 1260 (m),

774 (s) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 7.26–7.08 (5H, m, C_6H_5), 4.90 (1H, d, J 2.6 Hz, C_5H), 4.56 (1H, br, s, OH, exchanged in D_2O), 3.54 (1H, dd, J 2.2, 2.5 Hz, C_4H), 2.40 (1H, dt, J 3.0, 3.0 Hz, C_3H), 1.60 (2H, dt ~ m, CH_2 protons of $-\text{CH}_2-(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{OH}$), 1.52 (17H, m, cyclohexyl and CH_2 protons); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 170.22, 170.04 (carbonyl carbons), 132.68, 132.30, 131.54, 131.38 (aromatic carbons), 85.10 (C_5), 76.20 (C_3), 63.44 (CH_2OH), 56.70 (d), 37.32, 36.40, 33.69, 31.28, 30.55, 28.12, 26.90, 25.43, 24.20 (cyclohexyl and CH_2 carbons); FAB-MS : m/z 372 (M^+), 313, 299, 289, 222 (B.P), 216, 83, 77, 73, 59 (Found : C, 67.57; H, 7.45; N, 7.30. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires : C, 67.71; H, 7.56; N, 7.52%).

General procedure for synthesis of 1,3-amino alcohols (MWI) :

A mixture of isoxazolidine **2a** (100 mg) and Zn dust (5 mg) in dilute acetic acid (3 mL) was taken in a 25 mL Erlenmeyer flask, mixed well and subjected to microwave irradiation at 250 W for 9 min (entry 1). The completion of reaction was monitored by TLC (hexane : ethyl acetate = 5 : 1; R_f = 0.66). The reaction mixture was cooled to RT, extracted with diethyl ether and filtered. Excess acetic acid in the filtrate was removed through basic work up and finally column chromatographic purification results desired 1,3-amino alcohol in 84% yield (entry 1; Scheme 2; Table 2). This procedure was followed for other substrates listed in Table 2.

(3R,4S)-3-Hydroxy-4-((R)-5-hydroxy-1-(phenylamino)pentyl)-1-methylpyrrolidine-2,5-dione (2c) :

Yellowish white gummy liquid. Yield 84%, R_f = 0.66 (hexane : ethyl acetate = 5 : 1); IR (KBr) : ν_{max} 3650–3585 (br), 3510–3435 (br), 2845 (m), 1782 (s), 1685 (m), 1490 (m), 783 (s) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 7.05–6.88 (5H, m, C_6H_5), 5.24 (2H, br, 2 \times OH, exchanged in D_2O), 4.52 (1H, d, J 6.5 Hz, C_1H), 3.80 (1H, dd, J 6.5, 6.3 Hz, C_2H), 3.50 (1H, br, $-\text{NHC}_6\text{H}_5$), 3.36 (3H, s, CH_3 proton), 2.90 (1H, dt, J 6.3, 6.2 Hz, C_3H), 2.64 (2H, dt ~ m, CH_2 protons of $-\text{CH}_2-(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{OH}$), 2.12–1.65 (6H, m, CH_2 protons); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 173.70, 172.66 (carbonyl carbons), 129.94, 129.66, 129.14, 128.85 (aromatic carbons), 86.54 (C_1), 74.62 (C_3), 66.30 (CH_2OH), 55.08 (C_2), 33.12 (CH_3), 26.50, 24.22, 22.77 (3 CH_2 carbons); FAB-MS : m/z 306 (M^+), 233, 229, 156, 77, 73 (Found : C, 62.36; H, 7.06; N,

9.01. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires : C, 62.74; H, 7.23; N, 9.15%).

(3R,4S)-3-Hydroxy-4-((R)-5-hydroxy-1-(phenylamino)pentyl)-1-phenylpyrrolidine-2,5-dione (3c) :

White gummy liquid. Yield 81%, R_f = 0.68 (hexane : ethyl acetate = 5 : 1); IR (KBr) : ν_{max} 3670–3590 (br), 3505–3420 (br), 2840 (m), 1780 (s), 1680 (m), 1486 (m), 775 (s) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 7.22–7.08 (2 \times 5H, m, C_6H_5), 5.18–5.00 (2H, br, 2 \times OH, exchanged in D_2O), 4.80 (1H, d, J 6.7 Hz, C_1H), 3.76 (1H, dd, J 6.3, 6.3 Hz, C_2H), 3.43 (1H, br, $-\text{NHC}_6\text{H}_5$), 2.78 (1H, dt, J 6.4, 6.4 Hz, C_3H), 2.55 (2H, dt ~ m, CH_2 protons of $-\text{CH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{OH}$), 1.95–1.40 (6H, m, CH_2 protons); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 174.08, 172.55 (carbonyl carbons), 135.80, 135.47, 133.54, 133.11, 132.12, 130.80, 130.23, 129.90 (aromatic carbons), 85.66 (C_1), 75.20 (C_3), 63.90 (CH_2OH), 55.30 (C_2), 27.03, 24.80, 22.13 (3 CH_2 carbons); FAB-MS : m/z 368 (M^+), 295, 291, 218, 214, 77, 73 (Found : C, 68.33; H, 6.25; N, 7.28. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires : C, 68.47; H, 6.52; N, 7.60%).

(3R,4S)-1-Cyclohexyl-3-hydroxy-4-((R)-5-hydroxy-1-(phenylamino)pentyl)pyrrolidione-2,5-dione (4c) :

Dark gray gummy liquid. Yield 80%, R_f = 0.64 (hexane : ethyl acetate = 5 : 1); IR (KBr) : ν_{max} 3665–3580 (br), 3500–3425 (br), 2845 (m), 1778 (s), 1684 (m), 1440 (m), 1210 (m), 770 (s) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) : δ 6.83–6.66 (5H, m, C_6H_5), 5.22–5.09 (2H, br, 2 \times OH, exchanged in D_2O), 4.70 (1H, d, J 6.5 Hz, C_1H), 3.90 (1H, dd, J 6.8, 6.7 Hz, C_1H), 3.33 (1H, br, $-\text{NHC}_6\text{H}_5$), 2.60 (1H, dt, J 6.7, 6.2 Hz, C_1H), 2.28 (2H, dt ~ m, CH_2 protons of $-\text{CH}_2-(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{OH}$), 1.90–0.96 (17H, m, CH_2 protons); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 170.20, 170.05 (carbonyl carbons), 128.90, 128.56, 128.05, 127.66 (aromatic carbons), 86.22 (C_1), 74.28 (C_3), 62.50 (CH_2OH), 56.80 (C_2), 29.00, 28.45, 28.19, 27.06, 25.60, 23.86, 22.32, 20.72, 20.16 (CH_2 carbons); FAB-MS : m/z 374 (M^+), 301, 291, 224, 214, 83, 77, 73 (Found : C, 67.18; H, 7.88; N, 7.26. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires : C, 67.37; H, 8.02; N, 7.48%).

Conclusion :

This contribution represents an extension of our studies dealing with the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds having isoxazolidine and isoxazoline cores in their struc-

Note

ture. Further studies will be carried out in the near future to test their potential biological activities.

Acknowledgement

We are grateful to Dr. M. P. Kharel, Principal, Sikkim Government College for providing facilities and constant encouragement. We are pleased to acknowledge the financial support from UGC, New Delhi (Grant no : 34-304/2008-SR) and also to CDRI, Lucknow for providing spectral data.

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